

Nucleofuge effect : the kinetic and mechanistic studies of the reactions of some *O*-aryloximes and phenyl naphthyl ether with *n*-butylamine in acetonitrile

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The aminolysis reactions of *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-2-naphthol (DNPN), *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)indanoneoxime (DNPIO), and *O*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)propanoneoxime (DNPPO) have been carried out with *n*-butylamine in acetonitrile at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. The coloured product obtained in each case was *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)butylamine, in addition, in the case of DNPN, 2-naphthol was also obtained in quantitative yield. Second order rate constant, k_A increases linearly with increase in the base concentration. Mild catalysis has been observed during the reaction of *n*-butylamine with DNPN while no catalysis has been observed in the case of DNPIO and DNPPO. The observed order of reactivity is : DNPN > DNPIO > DNPPO. Mechanistic interpretation is given.

Aromatic nucleophilic substitution reactions are often base-catalyzed depending on the nature of the species expelled by the attacking nucleophile, i.e. the leaving group or nucleofuge. These reactions are strongly catalyzed by bases when a poor leaving group is present; with a good leaving group either mild or no catalysis is observed. The best leaving groups are those that stabilize the negative charge. The stability of the anion is related to basicity, the best leaving group, most often is the weakest base.

When nucleophilic attack occurs at a substituted ring position, substitution may result and the accepted mechanism¹ for reaction with amine nucleophiles is shown in Scheme 1.

Scheme 1

On applying steady state approximation to Scheme 1, the kinetic expression initially proposed by Orvic and Bunnett¹ may be represented as

$$\frac{\text{Rate}}{[\text{Arx}][\text{Nu}]} = k_A = \frac{k_1(k_2 + k_3[\text{B}])}{k_{-1} + k_2 + k_3[\text{B}]}$$

where k_A stands for second order rate coefficient of aminolysis and B for the base molecule. The base-catalyzed pathway may involve rate-limiting proton transfer from the zwitterionic intermediate to base, or general acid catalysis

(by BH^+) of leaving group expulsion from an anionic intermediate in rapid equilibrium with zwitterion. The latter pathway, the SB-GA mechanism, has been shown to be generally applicable to reactions involving displacement of alkoxy groups by amines in DMSO. Thus Orvik and Bunnett¹ were able to observe in separate steps the formation of anionic intermediates and their acid-catalyzed conversion to substitution products. Forlanni² compared the nucleofugicity of nitro and chloro groups (as leaving groups) in the reactions of 2-nitrothiazole, 2-nitrobenzothiazole with some nucleophiles and explained difference in reactivity on the basis of hydrogen bond formation between the leaving group and the solvent or the nucleophile. Akopjivi *et al.*³ studied the effect of nucleofuge on the reactions of 2,4-dinitrofluorobenzene and observed that in acetonitrile the reaction was uncatalyzed with *n*-butylamine but showed a curvilinear response with morpholine.

Much kinetic data have been reported in the literature on aromatic substitution reactions with halogen, alkoxy, aryloxy or amine as a leaving group^{4,5}. In few cases substrates with bulky and sterically congested leaving groups have been studied⁶. In view of great interest for data on sterically bulky nucleofuges on nucleophilic substitution, we report here the kinetic studies of the reactions of *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)-2-naphthyl phenyl ether (DNPN), *O*-(2',4'-dinitrophenyl)indanoneoxime (DNPIO) and *O*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)propanoneoxime (DNPPO) with *n*-butylamine in acetonitrile (dipolar aprotic solvent) at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$. In the present study, no catalysis was observed with DNPIO, DNPPO while a mild catalysis observed during the reaction of *n*-butylamine with DNPN. This may be due to the pecu-

liar nature of the substrate. It has a better leaving group and at the same time the intermediate complex is more stable due to extended delocalization.

Results and discussion

The reactions of 1, 2 and 3 with *n*-butylamine were followed spectrophotometrically in acetonitrile at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$ under pseudo-first order conditions at 351 nm.

The coloured product obtained in each case was *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)butylamine, in addition in the case of DNPN, 2-naphthol was also found in quantitative yield. The results are summarized in Table 1.

The plots of k_0 vs [*n*-butylamine], k_A vs [*n*-butylamine] are given in Figs. 1 and 2, respectively. From these plots values of k'' and k' have been evaluated for the reactions of DNPN, DNPIO and DNPPO; the values of k''/k' are 110, 29 and 39 mol dm⁻³, respectively. It is apparent that only

Fig. 1. Reactions of (●) DNPN, (■) DNPIO and (▲) DNPPO with *n*-butylamine in acetonitrile at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$, first order plots, [subs] = 4×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³.

Fig. 2. Reactions of (●) DNPN, (■) DNPIO and (▲) DNPPO with *n*-butylamine in acetonitrile at $35 \pm 0.1^\circ$, second order plots, [subs] = 4×10^{-5} mol dm⁻³.

Table 1. Rate constants for the reactions of DNPN, DNPIO and DNPPO with *n*-butylamine in acetonitrile

Substrate	$10^{-3}[n\text{-Butylamine}]$ mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³	$10^{-4}k_0$ s ⁻¹	$10^{-2}K_A$ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹ dm ⁻³	k''/k' mol ⁻¹ dm ⁻³
DNPN	2.00	5.52	27.55	110.00
	4.00	12.77	31.93	
	6.00	21.93	36.55	
	7.00	27.36	39.08	
	8.00	33.75	42.19	
DNPIO	3.00	4.46	14.87	28.57
	4.00	6.34	15.84	
	5.00	7.99	15.97	
	5.50	8.99	16.33	
	6.00	10.51	17.52	
DNPPO	2.00	1.42	7.11	39.16
	3.00	2.05	6.82	
	3.50	2.41	6.89	
	4.00	2.82	7.03	
	5.00	3.54	7.07	
	5.50	3.90	7.08	
	6.00	4.22	7.04	
	7.00	4.95	7.07	
8.00	5.74	7.18		

mild catalysis occurs in the case of DNPN while the reactions are mostly uncatalyzed in the other cases. The second order rate constant k_A was obtained by dividing the first order rate constant k_0 by [amine]. The order of reactivity is DNPN > DNPIO > DNPPO. The plots of k_A vs [amine] are

Table 2. Activation parameters for the reactions of DNPN, DNPIO and DNPPPO with *n*-butylamine in acetonitrile

Substrate	$10^{-2}K_A$ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹ dm ³	E_a kJ mol ⁻¹	A mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹ dm ³	ΔS^\ddagger J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	ΔH^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔG^\ddagger kJ mol ⁻¹
DNPN	36.88	40.61 ±(0.47)	2.84×10^6 ±(0.06)	29.93 ±(0.03)	38.05 ±(0.06)	78.08 ±(0.93)
DNPIO	17.4	43.23 ±(0.51)	3.74×10^6 ±(0.00)	127.68 ±(0.01)	40.67 ±(0.01)	79.99 ±(0.00)
DNPPPO	7.09	38.89 ±(1.29)	2.79×10^5 ±(0.06)	149.26 ±(0.16)	82.30 ±(0.05)	36.33 ±(0.01)

linear with positive slopes and intercepts. The experimental rate law is given by eqn. (2),

$$k_A = k' + k'' [B] \quad (2)$$

where k' ($=k_1 k_2 / k_{-1}$, the intercept) is non-catalytic and catalytic and k'' ($=k_1 k_3 / k_{-1}$, the slope) the catalytic rate constants. Scheme 1 is established^{1,4} by interpretation of eqn. (2).

The kinetic data are summarized in Table 1, and the other relevant data of the reactions are given in Table 2. In many aromatic nucleophilic substitution reactions small increase in k_A with increasing nucleophile (on more generally, added

Scheme 2

base) concentration is observed. The values of k''/k' are small (>50) and the accelerating effect of the bases bears no relationship to their base strength. According to Bunnett and Garst⁷, this does not represent true base-catalysis, the formation of the intermediate is rate-determining in these reactions, and small increases are due to some unspecified effect. In the case of DNPN, increase in the base concentration has more accelerating effect compared to DNPIO and DNPPPO, the value of k''/k' is higher than 50 and the catalytic effect increases with the increase in strength of the base. The reaction is regarded as base-catalyzed and the decomposition of the intermediate is rate-limiting. The values of k''/k' for the reactions of DNPIO, DNPPPO and DNPN are 29.0, 39.0 and 110.0, respectively. According to Bunnett's criteria these low values (29.0, 39.0) do not represent true base-catalysis. The appropriate mechanism is often referred to as the SB-GA (Scheme 2).

Another way of increasing the susceptibility of a system to base-catalysis is to decrease the nucleofugicity of the leaving group. Thus the reaction of DNPN with *n*-butylamine in acetonitrile is catalyzed while the others are not.

Difference in reactivity :

The nucleophilic reactivity of the aromatic carbon is mainly due to the combined electron-withdrawing effect of the two nitro groups and also the inherent tendency of the bonded oxygen of Ar---O bond to attract electrons towards itself. As far as the influence of the nitro group is concerned, all the three substrates are equally exposed to it and no difference in reactivity is envisaged on this account.

Scheme 3

A comparison of the structures of the substrates (1-3) reveals that DNPN is phenylnaphthyl ether whereas DNPIO and DNPPPO are oxime ethers. The order of observed reac-

tivity is $\text{DNPN} > \text{DNPIO} > \text{DNPPO}$. The highest reactivity in the case of DNPN is attributed to efficient delocalization of charge of the intermediate σ -complex in which the π -electron cloud is delocalized over two phenyl rings in the naphthalene moiety, and attributes better stability to the leaving group. The naphthoxide ion is more stable compared to the other two leaving groups. In the case of DNPIO, delocalization occurs to a lesser extent compared DNPN and in the case of DNPPO, electron delocalization is almost negligible. Intermediate complex formed in this reaction is shown in Scheme 3.

Site of nucleophilic attack :

All the kinetic data pertaining to the aminolysis reactions of oxime ethers in dipolar aprotic solvent, i.e. acetonitrile are in conformity with the fairly established mechanism of nucleophilic aromatic substitution. Product analysis by spectral as well as TLC studies have confirmed formation of coloured aminolysis product, *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)butylamine in quantitative yield in each case. Physical characteristics of amination product of **2** are : m.p. 84° ; R_f 0.95 (C_6H_6 : CHCl_3 , 1 : 1); λ_{max} 351.5 nm ($\log \epsilon$ 4.23 acetonitrile). Hence the site of nucleophilic attack has been located at the nitroactivated aromatic carbon attached to the oxime oxygen resulting in C–O bond cleavage.

An alternative possibility of a nucleophilic attack at the sp^2 oxime nitrogen, may be ruled out on the basis of the following experiment :

Attack at oxime nitrogen

Experimentally not observed

(i) Such an attack at the oxime nitrogen should always result in N–O bond cleavage giving 2,4-dinitrophenoxide ion as one of the reaction products, which could not be detected.

Attack at aromatic carbon

Experimentally observed

(ii) Had there been an attack on the oxime nitrogen resulting in N–O bond cleavage, observation of general base catalysis and several characteristics of nucleophilic aromatic substitution reactions encountered in the present study would not have been observed.

In the case of DNPN, two attacking sites, both aromatic, one being on the benzene ring and the other the naphthyl ring are available. A comparison of TLC as well as spectral studies of products with authentic sample revealed the formation of *N*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)amine and 2-naphthol in quantitative yield.

Temperature effect :

The effect of temperature was studied for the reactions of DNPN, DNPIO and DNPPO with *n*-butylamine in acetonitrile under pseudo-first order conditions in the range 25 – 45° for DNPIO, DNPPO, but in the case of DNPN the range was 20 – 35° . The rate constants were found to fit the Arrhenius equation well. The second order rate constant (k_A) decreases from DNPN to DNPPO (Table 2). The magnitude of entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) increases from DNPN to DNPPO. The large negative values of the entropy of activation are compatible with considerable change in the charge distribution between the ground and transition state. Generally ΔS^\ddagger values are more negative for bimolecular processes⁸. The negative value is dependent on the number of reactant molecules brought in to an orderly arrangement in the transition state⁹. Differences in the rates were mostly governed by differences in the enthalpy of activation. The large negative values of entropy of activation observed in each case support the formation of the sterically congested transition state.

Experimental

Acetonitrile (E. Merck) was used as such. The nucleophile, *n*-butylamine (Fluka) was used after distillation.

Equimolar mixture of β -naphthol (5 g, 0.03 mol) and 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene (6 g, 0.03 mol) dissolved in benzene was warmed for a few minutes. After evaporation of benzene, the resulting light yellow coloured crystalline compound was crystallized from ethanol.

O-(2',4'-Dinitrophenyl)-2-naphthol (DNPN, **1**) : It had m.p. 78° ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1340, 1520 (NO_2), 1535 (aromatic), 750 cm^{-1} (fused ring); δ (90 MHz; CDCl_3) 7.1–8.9 (10H, m, ArH).

The oximes of the substrates DNPPO and DNPIO were prepared by reported procedure¹⁰. An equimolar mixture of oxime, 1-chloro-2,4-dinitrobenzene and sodium methoxide in methanol was warmed (15 min) and allowed to stand. The coloured precipitate obtained after evaporation of methanol was crystallized from ethanol. Crystals of *O*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)propanoneoxime, and *O*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)indanoneoxime were obtained :

O-(2',4'-Dinitrophenyl)indanoneoxime (DNPIO, **2**), m.p. 75°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1523, 1350 (NO₂), 1530 (aromatic), 1610 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 3.08 (4H, m), 7.97–8.87 (7H, m, ArH).

O-(2,4-Dinitrophenyl)propanoneoxime (DNPPO, **3**), m.p. 56°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1345, 1525 (NO₂), 1535 (aromatic), 1610 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ (90 MHz; CDCl₃) 2.3 (3H, s), 2.42 (3H, s), 7.35–8.78 (3H, m, ArH).

Kinetic procedure : Reactions were studied spectrophotometrically on a Shimadzu UV 2100 spectrophotometer under pseudo-first order conditions at 315 nm and at 35 ± 0.1° in acetonitrile. The first order coefficients (k_o) were obtained by least-squares method from a plot of $\log (A_\alpha - A_o) / (A_\alpha - A_t)$ vs time, where A_α , A_t and A_o are the absorbance at infinity, at time t and zero, respectively. Second order rate constants (k_A) were obtained from the slope of a plot of k_o vs [amine] at more than four concentrations of *n*-butylamine.

The description of a typical kinetic run with *n*-butylamine follows : A mixture containing CH₃CN (0.4 ml) and *n*-butylamine solution (5 × 10⁻³ mol dm⁻³; 2.6 ml) in acetonitrile was taken in a covered quartz cuvette and kept in the thermostated cell compartment at 35 ± 0.1°. The substrate solution (1.0 ml) in acetonitrile, thermostated at the same temperature, was injected into the above mixture by a precalibrated clinical syringe. Care was taken to ensure thorough mixing. The absorbance was recorded immediately at 351 nm corresponding to the λ_{\max} of *O*-(2,4-dinitrophenyl)-*n*-butylamine at various time intervals covering at least four half-lives and the infinite reading was recorded after ten half-lives of the reaction. Reproducibility of measurements was

verified from at least two sets of identical runs. The reaction products were characterized on the basis of comparison of spectral data and R_f values with those of the authentic samples.

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